

THE USE OF ANCESTRAL HERITAGE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE TEACHER'S SPIRITUAL IMAGE.

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Abstract: This article examines the teachings of our great ancestors in developing the spiritual image of the teacher. In addition, the opinions of our great ancestors on the development of the teacher's spiritual image are classified.

Since the creation of man, the endowment of consciousness and thought has caused him to constantly undergo stages of cultural development. It is difficult to imagine this cultural development without educational development. The art of pedagogy, which is one of the great roots of human thought, has an ancient history in our country. The history of pedagogic art and its related sources, like all fields of science, have been well studied by our scientists so far.

has gone through various stages of development until the generation of mankind was formed and reached its present form. In the early days, their daily life consisted only of scavenging and finding food to eat and fill their stomachs. As a result of the struggle for survival, in order to collect enough food, he managed to make complex weapons from simple hunting weapons. This process began to have a great impact on people's minds and thinking.

Today, we are living in a historical period in which the cultural heritage of our people is being restored and presented to the world community. A period of renewal always begins with an incomparable increase in interest in the past. This is also related to the development and learning of the art of pedagogy, which is the core of our cultural heritage. Past events, historical events clarify our conclusions today, show the basis and reality of our plans for tomorrow.

of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan (April 30, 2023). Article 61 states that citizens must preserve the historical, spiritual, cultural, scientific and natural heritage of the people of Uzbekistan[1].

Not only preserving the historical, spiritual, cultural, scientific and natural heritage of the people of Uzbekistan, but also using it in the educational process will positively help in solving important tasks. For this, it is very important for us to study the spiritual, cultural, scientific and natural heritage of our great grandfathers and use it wisely in our pedagogical activities.

It is especially noteworthy that our great-grandfathers were considerate, benevolent, demanding and respectful towards the teaching profession and the owners of this profession.

Today's era of development has not reached such heights by itself. How many great scholars, geniuses, teachers, scholars lived and created on this road. And they spent their whole lives on education and on realizing the good intentions of mankind.

In history, reflections on the delicacy, responsibility, complexity and honor of the teacher's profession, the teacher's skills, requirements for them, views on his qualities, communication skills, culture of behavior were expressed in the works of Eastern thinkers.

Eastern pedagogy and pedagogical skills have a thousand-year history. Various aspects of Eastern spiritual culture, especially in the period of Eastern Renaissance, were very developed. Abu Nasr Farabi, Al-Khorazmi, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Baghdad scholar Nasriddin Tusi, Timurid period cooks Abdurrahman Jami, who lived and worked during this period. The works of Jalaluddin Devoni, Alisher Navoiy and many other thinkers serve as an important resource for the spiritual and moral maturity of young coaches in the development of pedagogical thinking.

In particular, the great scholar of the East, the encyclopedist Abu Nasr Farabi (873-950) put forward instructive ideas about the role of the teacher in social life and its characteristics. In his opinion, "a teacher should have intelligence, a beautiful speech, and be able to fully and clearly express the thoughts he wants to convey to students. At the same time, he should value his dignity and be fair. Only then will he have a high level of humanity and reach the peak of happiness," he says. Farabi is a great teacher who has the ability to objectively, fairly and rationally comment on a number of qualities characteristic of a teacher. Therefore, these comments, scientific applications, deep thoughts, instructive comments have not lost their relevance.

According to the famous scientist Abu Ali ibn Sina (980-1037), who commented on this problem, "... A teacher should be a person who is tenacious, has a clear conscience, is honest, and knows well the methods of raising children and the rules of ethics. The teacher should be able to study the entire inner and outer world of the student and get into the layers of his mind." According to Abu Ali ibn Sina, the teacher must first love, respect and be kind to children. If the child does the work well, he should be encouraged at the right time, sometimes praised, and if not, he should be reprimanded. But, says Ibn Sina, the reprimand should not affect the child's dignity, and making concessions to the student will lead to the child becoming independent, says Ibn Sina.

Nasriddin Tusi (1201-1272, Baghdad) says in his work "On Education of Teachers": "A teacher should be able to conduct debates, know how to prove irrefutably, believe in the correctness of his thoughts, and his speech should be absolutely clean, and his sentences should be logically expressed." .. The teacher's speech can never and anywhere be poisonous, rude and harsh. "The teacher's lack of self-control during the lesson can spoil the work," says Alloma.

About the teacher and his skills, the works of our grandfather Abdurrahman Jami, the sultan of poetry, Alisher Navoi, and other scholars contain valuable, masterpiece thoughts about the teacher's ability, personal qualities, his speech, the art of oratory, and culture. The great thinker Abdurrahman Jami in his works highly appreciates the role of the school and the teacher in the development of the child's outlook. In his opinion, a teacher should be intelligent, fair, and embody all the highest qualities. It suggests that a person who behaves inappropriately will never be able to impart knowledge to others.

Master, time without a teacher,

The world would be black because of ignorance, - he exclaims in the work "Iskandar Khirodnoma".

The genius of Uzbek literature, Alisher Navoi, in his works and scientific views, makes instructive comments about the teaching ability, his reputation, and manners. According to Alloma, he cannot imagine the work of a teacher without a creative approach. He says that he always needs to work on himself perfectly and gain experience. That is why in his works the qualities of decency, morality, intelligence, willpower, purity, and sincerity occupy the main place. He pointed out that the teacher's being an example and example in all respects is a guarantee of education and training (Table 1).

Table 1.
Thoughtful thoughts of our thinker grandfathers about teachers-coaches

Tr	Thinkers	thoughts
1	Abu Nasr Pharoah	It is necessary for a teacher to have intelligence, a beautiful speech, and to be able to fully and clearly express the thoughts he wants to convey to students. At the same time, he should value his dignity and be fair. Only then will he have a high level of humanity and reach the peak of happiness
2	Abu Ali ibn Sina	A teacher should be a person who is tenacious, honest, honest and well-versed in child-rearing methods and rules of ethics. The teacher should be able to study the inner and outer world of the student and get into the layers of his mind. The teacher must first love, respect and be kind to children. If the child does the work well, he should be encouraged at the right time, sometimes praised, and if not, he should be reprimanded. However, the reprimand should not affect the child's dignity, and compromising the student will lead to the child becoming independent.
3	Baghdad scientist Nasriddin Tusi ,	In his work "On Educating Teachers", he says: "A teacher must conduct discussions, know how to prove irrefutably, believe in the correctness of his thoughts, and his speech must be absolutely clean, and his sentences must be logically expressed... The teacher's speech is never and nowhere poisonous, can't be rough and tough. A teacher's lack of self-control during a lesson can spoil the work
4	Abdurrahman Jami,	He greatly appreciates the role of the school and the teacher in the development of the child's outlook. In his opinion, a teacher should be intelligent, fair, and embody all the highest qualities. It suggests that a person who behaves inappropriately will never be able to impart knowledge to others. Master, time without a teacher, The world would be black because of ignorance, - he exclaims in the work "Iskandar Khirodnoma".

5	Alisher Navoi	According to the general public, the work of a teacher cannot be imagined without a creative approach. He says that he always needs to work on himself perfectly and gain experience. That is why in his works the qualities of decency, morality, intelligence, willpower, purity, and sincerity occupy the main place. He pointed out that the teacher should be an example and a role model in all respects, which is the guarantee of education and upbringing	
6	Abdulla Avloni	creative research, searching for new forms, methods and tools of reading and teaching is one of the most important qualities of a teacher	

In addition, comments on the essence of training the teacher's professional skills are also described in such great works as "Nightmare", "Hotamnoma", "Kutadgu Bilig". Because all these works are the origin of etiquette, the stages of formation of the unique qualities of the educator-coach are expressed.

Abdulla Avloni, one of the founders of the modernist movement in Turkestan in the 19th and 20th centuries, a great enlightener, teacher, skilled researcher, is a scientist who has a completely new approach to the problems of the educational system, teaching, improving the qualifications of teachers, and training future teachers. According to him, creative research, searching for new forms, methods and tools of reading and teaching is one of the most important qualities of a teacher.

Thus, Central Asian thinkers and Uzbek enlighteners believe that a teacher should have a strong memory, will and thinking, intelligence, beautiful speech, show zeal and determination in the way of achieving the intended goal, be able to find the right way to the spiritual world of students, influence them, be conscientious, they emphasize in their works that it is necessary to act as a sincere, polite, feminine, hardworking, responsible person[5].

In conclusion, it can be said that the use of the spiritual and educational heritage of our great ancestors serves as an important resource for improving the spiritual image of modern pedagogues.

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